

	<p>Quantumacy: Quantum key distribution for large-scale informational self-determination, privacy-aware and distributed processing of personal sensitive medical data</p> <p>Public report v 1.0 – 15/01/2023</p> <p><i>CERN, Be-ys Research</i></p>
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Executive summary

With the COVID-19 pandemic, our globalised world has engaged faster in digitalisation, and so has healthcare which is becoming one of the main developing sectors for digitalised services. CERN and Be-ys Research have initiated in 2018 the Living Lab project, which aims at developing a network of labs to investigate GDPR-compliant healthcare data systems. In QUANTUMACY we have extended the concept to work on the design and implementation of a Proof-of-Concept of secure data architecture integrating QKD-based implementations of blockchain (for secure transactions), homomorphic encryption (for secure storage and analysis), SMPC (for transfers and analysis), and channel encryption as a means of providing core services requiring key issuance and distribution, and to shape a new approach to making data available and processed under the so-called principle of polymorphic privacy. The project provides a few test use cases of the PoC on simple but realistic conditions in collaboration with healthcare research institutes in the Living Labs network, exploiting existing expertise developed as part of equivalent non-quantum implementations that provide a baseline for comparison.

Main results

At the end of its 12-month programme between March 2021 and February 2022, QUANTUMACY has developed a QKD simulation environment based on the BB84 protocol with simple noise simulation to test the feasibility of deploying secure end-to-end data analysis applications using sensitive data. The demo environment was set up at CERN on a private cluster using simulated QKD and then extended with a real QKD link established between the CERN Data Centre in Meyrin (Geneva) and the IDQ Data Centre hosted by SIG in Geneva. A number of use cases use cases have been and are being deployed on the demonstration platform at <https://quantumacy.cern.ch> :

QKD generation and distribution: Use secure keys generated by simulated and real QKD links to exchange data and secure communication across client-server and federated services. The transmitted data was further encrypted using a homomorphic encryption scheme based on the Microsoft SEAL library.

Health Check Score: A demo to show how to protect the privacy of personal information transmitted through Internet connections using QKD and homomorphic encryption in patient/doctor communication. The demo asks as to input a set of data relevant for cardiovascular risk assessment, encrypts the data with HE, transmits the data on a QKD secure channel, evaluated the risks on the server without decrypting the data, and finally retransmit the results to the client.

Chest MRI Classification: A demo to show how to implement a simple image classification pipeline over QKD-secured networks using homomorphically-encrypted images. The demo provides a random set of MRI chest images containing both front and later scans, encrypts and transmits the image to a processing server and return the classification of the images as front or lateral.

Secure Federated Learning: A demo to explain how to extend Federated Learning frameworks (specifically openFL) to use symmetric keys generated by QKD to secure the communication between the computing nodes.

Parkinson's Symptoms Classification: A demo that uses the secure federated learning platform to classify Parkinson's tremor symptoms from wearable and portable sensor devices. The links between the analysis nodes are all secured using QKD keys.

Secure Block Chains: A demo showing an example of a block chain framework to record and validate transactions across a distributed data analysis pipeline using keys generated by the QKD infrastructure and homomorphic encryption.

Lessons learned

Setting up real QKD links was not straightforward, some familiarity with the equipment and the fibre network quality requirements and multiple passes of cleaning and tuning were required. However, once the links were established, using the keys as part of the different functionality provided by the platform was straightforward. The range of potential applications is considerable and can have high impact on improving security, confidentiality and trust.

Outlook

The project was an excellent case of living lab, where QKD experts, security experts, applications developers and end users could interact to discuss requirements and define challenges. The platform was designed as a proof-of-concept where integration of different technologies and potential applications could be explored in a relatively lightweight environment. For realistic applications a more thorough assessment of the end-to-end security of the data pipelines, the possible attack points, and weaknesses is clearly necessary. However, this initial demonstration has allowed to gather interesting insights in the design of future QKD-secured infrastructures.